

netWorked Youth Research for Empowerment in the Digital society

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Second Cycle Activity Toolkit

WP6_D6.2

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1 Introduction

Based on the results gathered during the 1st Cycle of the WYRED project (García-Peñalvo, 2016b, 2017, 2018; García-Peñalvo & Kearney, 2016; Griffiths et al., 2017), the following version has been drafted to help moderators present the idea and processes behind a generative research project to young learners with little or no previous experience. A simplified language has been used, as far as possible, in order to make the approach more understandable. In order to establish the suitability of the students' version of the activity toolkit, it was presented to young learners across Istanbul, who provided invaluable feedback.

1.1.1 What is research?

Research is something we do to find out more about a topic that interests us. Usually, we would ask ourselves a question relating to a specific topic. For instance: why does it rain?

We look for information in books, in newspapers, on the internet. We can also ask people what they know about a specific topic. This means we are looking for facts. We are looking for information that will help us to answer the question.

However, we can also try to find out how people feel about a specific topic. In this case, we are looking for opinions and may ask something like: how does rain make you feel?

Either way, a research allows us to collect information which we can use for a bigger project. In fact, the research is always a starting point, never a point of arrival.

1.1.2 Why do we do research?

We can learn many new things by doing research, we can discover new topics or simply gain a new understanding of a topic we already know. We may do research because we want to discover new ways of solving existing problems, or because we want to discover if particular problems do exist. We may also want to do research simply because it is fun.

Doing research can be compared like going on a long journey. At the end of the journey, we will have lots of memories we may treasure, with photographs and diary entries etc. to keep those memories fresh. We will be able to talk about the places we have visited, what we saw and what impressed us. However, on the journey we will also have learned many things, like reading maps, understanding the compass, speaking different languages, tasting new food, etc. When we do research, the journey is as important as the destination. What is particularly interesting about this kind of journey is that when we set off, we have an idea of where we are going, we have a sense of general direction, but we rarely know where we will actually end up.

Doing research can be particularly fun if leads to create something. This kind of research, where we think of ideas around a specific problem and create solutions for the problem, is called generative research. This means that as part of the research, something has been '*generated*': this can be anything from a photo album to a log, from a video to a fully functioning new product.

In order to generate something useful, it is important that the problem for which a solution is being sought is properly understood. This means that a lot of data about the problem has to be collected and analysed.

For many researchers, it can be particularly interesting if they can meet and talk to many different people. They do this by conducting interviews which they previously prepare, or by simply

observing people. This allows them to understand how people behave in certain situations, why they behave in a certain way, what they like or dislike, what they are capable of and what they would like to be able to do, etc.

1.1.3 How shall we start doing a WYRED research?

There have been many conversations in WYRED so far, about what children and young people around Europe feel particularly strongly about. Those conversations have been summarised in what was called the 'dialogues', and they can be a good source of inspiration for a topic to research. Based on the topic, we can start asking many questions for which we would like to find an answer. This can be done individually, or in a group. Once we have found a question that we particularly like, we are ready to move to the next step. However, there are at least a couple of things which are important to bear in mind (See also Table 2 below, Step-by-Step Guide):

- the original question we want the research to answer may change, depending on what we will find along the way; we may even end up asking many new questions!
- the question we are going to ask will receive a different answer depending on where we are and on what is around us; for instance, 'Why does it rain?' will receive different answers if we are in England, in the desert, or on the moon! Our specific situation and the environment around us are also called 'context', and context is very important in research.

1.1.4 Select a research method

At this stage, we have made a decision of approximately where we want to go. So now we need to decide how we want to get there. Like for a journey, we may decide to choose one way of transport only to realise later on that it is not an ideal solution; but this is ok, we learn along the way and we can adjust as needed.

When doing research, the way we carry it out is called a 'method'. There are many different research methods, and the choice depends on various aspects. For instance, some methods are more suited to specific questions, some researchers may simply have their personal preference. Table 1 below will give you an idea of what methods you could try; review them with your moderator and choose the one you think fits best.

1.1.4.1 [Get organised](#)

If you are going to do a research as part of a group, you will need to decide who is going to do what, and by when. This is called to assign roles and responsibilities. Make sure everyone is comfortable within their role, and remember that more than one person can cover the same role. As a group, try to think of all the things you will need to do and write them down. Once you have a list of tasks, you can put them in chronological order (i.e. which tasks need to be completed first, which depend on previous tasks, etc.) and assign them to a member of the group. Ask your moderator to assist you.

If you are going to do a research on your own, you should still draft a list of tasks and then review it at least with your moderator. This will help you to identify which tasks are important, and in which order you need to complete them.

A good way to build a list of tasks is to start with the end. Ask yourself the question: What do we want to be able to show at the end of the research? For instance, this could be a video uploaded on YouTube with an animation showing potential causes for rain. With this in mind, you can start thinking what you need and work your way backwards along the list of tasks.

Please note that it is also very important that you are realistic about what you can achieve, given the time you have available, the opportunities to travel you may have, the access to people to talk to, etc.

1.1.4.2 [Carry out the research](#)

At this stage, you will mainly be looking for information and collecting data. You will need to think about how you want to gather data. If you are going to interview people, you can start by thinking who may be in a position to provide useful data, how many people you want to involve, who you may need to contact, who may be able to help, etc.

Bear in mind that collecting data takes time, so you will have to be patient and persistent. At the same time, be mindful that those you are interviewing may not have much time to dedicate to your research.

Make sure you keep record of the information you collect, and that you organise the data by type, or topic, so that you can easily find it later on. Do not just write down the data you collect or the findings you make, but also the steps you have taken. For this purpose, consult Annex 1 (Support template for the research activity), as well as Table 2 below.

1.1.4.3 [Draw your conclusions](#)

Once you have collected enough data, you will need to summarise it and to draw conclusions. Ideally, you will already have decided what you want to show (see also 4.1. above). As you are putting the final pieces together, you may want to ask someone you know to have a look at it, and let you know what they think. This will help you spot potential issues, so you can fix them before completing the work.

1.1.4.4 [Show and tell](#)

Once you feel the work is done, ask your moderator to show you how to publicise it within the WYRED network and beyond. It is in the common interest that your findings are shared by as many people as possible. Think of school publications, local newspapers, but also social media as place to have your story and your findings told.

2 Generative Research Methods

2.1 Definition

Below you will find a few examples from the first two project cycles of WYRED, which may inspire you to carry out a research. Try to look at the research method as well as at the research topic, to help you decide. Are there any activities that particularly interest you, or that you would find particularly difficult to follow? For every example, you can also come up with your own variations and suggestions. If you do, please share with your moderator so they can share with the whole WYRED community.

1. Classic research projects

Classic research projects will typically look at one of three areas:

- An aspect that has not been researched yet, or not sufficiently enough
- Continue or expand a research already done;
- replicate a research in a different context.
- In any case, a research project will follow a specific method, and will put the new learnings to good used – in other words, the research will not be done just for the sake of it.

SAMPLE FROM ITALY

Project name: DIGITAL INNOVATION, TECHNOLOGY AND LEARNING

We created a survey about Digital Parts in education which was filled in by young people (majority of, female) from Italy, and these are their answers.

Checked situation online. As found:

- Education needs a huge improvement to follow digital innovation.
- These changes may pass through innovative pedagogy.
- Teachers and educators need to improve their digital competences and knowledge on digital education through trainings.
- Non-formal education paradigms could be proven helpful in the process of enhancing education's digital aspect.
- With the help of technological educational tools, students and young people would start learning independently and getting a deep knowledge of their personal learning mechanisms.

Project link from WYRED platform: <https://platform.wyredproject.eu/community/necessary-changes-education/project/digital-innovation-technology-and-learning>

SAMPLE FROM TURKEY

Project name: GENDER BIASED IDIOMS, IN THE PAST AND NOW

While examining the lives of societies, we should have opinion about their culture, languages, and some concepts that indicate the features of this language. Idioms are incredibly amazing to evaluate the perception of a society towards women, education, social life e.g. because idioms are word groups that reflect people's experiences and keep the stream of narration vivid. In the project, 18 idioms were detected from The Turkish Language Association- Proverbs and Idioms dictionary that include gender oriented idioms in order to comprehend much better the perception of Turkish society's perception towards women and show off the negative aspects of this perception, define the negative sides of these idioms and these idioms were classified and examined in two categories as the women's intellectual statute and the statute of women in the society; some codes that had negative viewpoint were determined and classified according to their categories. In the search conducted with the content analysis method, the detected 18 idioms contained negative viewpoint towards women were determined. It was seen that the statute of women in the society were behind men in the aspects of intellectual and social, the role of a woman in the society was only being a mother and caring the house so the conscious of being women's equal rights with men in each field couldn't be developed well according to the examined idioms.

Project link from the WYRED platform:

<https://platform.wyredproject.eu/community/do%C4%9Fa-community/project/doga-school-projects>

2. Creative projects

When a research project is set up in such a way that researchers collaborate to design and produce something original, it can be called a 'creative project'. This does not necessarily have to be a work of art, as creativity can be applied in all walks of life.

SAMPLE FROM TURKEY

Project name: THE ENVIRONMENTALLY FRIENDLY ROOFS: TO OBTAIN ENERGY FROM RAIN WATER ON THE ROOFS SHAPED IN THE FORM OF M

The concept of energy and energy resources have taken place among the most crucial subjects from past to today. People have begun to use energy resources insensibly via the increasing industrialization. For this reason, using the renewable resources instead of the fossil resources has an increased tendency recently. To obtain electricity from the movement of water means hydroelectric energy. It comes in the first order in the renewable resources. %40 electricity need of our country is supplied from this energy resources. Due to hydroelectric power stations' cost is relatively economical, the government invest heavily in these resources. Resources should be increased since the usage of energy is getting more and more day by day. So, in our project, it is aimed to obtain energy from the water gathered on the roofs designed in the form of M in the regions of getting much rain for the sake of increasing hydroelectric resources. While this work was being done, the photo block was used. The house's walls and the roof shaped M were composed with this material. A narrower partition shaped V supplied of gathering water flowing to the end part of the roof was made. In the following, the blades of the water turbine under the roof was turned by spilling water from the end part of the roof. Via the moving dynamo attached to the water turbine, the occurring light was observed in the led lamps. Finally, the turning of the water turbine and composing energy by the movement of the flowing water was observed.

Project link from the WYRED platform;

<https://platform.wyredproject.eu/community/do%C4%9Fa-community/project/doga-school-projects>

3. Journalistic research

This type of research can be done individually or in a team. The following principles need to be applied:

- The work must be as accurate as possible (get the facts right);
- The research cannot take sides (be impartial, only seek the truth);
- Researchers must be willing to admit errors and correct them, if they realise they got something wrong (be honest and accountable)
- Researchers protect their sources (respect the right of individuals who tell you something to remain anonymous).

Imagine you are a reporter and want to find out information about something. You will identify people to interview, places to visit, data to research and analyse, etc. Once you feel you have collected enough information, you will summarise it all in the format of a newspaper article, or a magazine article, or a blog, or even a short film.

Whilst the internet may sound like the ideal starting point to research information, always be aware of the following:

- The internet has too much information, so it will be difficult to identify what is useful and what is not;
- Not all information on the internet is correct, so it will not be easy to always identify what is accurate and what is not;
- If it is on the internet, a lot of people will already have read it, so it will be difficult to produce something new or original.

However, not everything is on the internet! Some information has not been digitised yet (e.g. historical documents, records held in microfiches), is not publicly shared (e.g. sensitive information about legal, economic, civic topics etc.) or, simply, has not been gathered yet.

Instead of or as well as searching on the internet, you can also do the following:

- Interview people of interest; this is a great method to gather information, or to receive useful indications on where to look further. Make sure you know beforehand what questions you will want to ask, and draft a list of potential interviewees on the subject. Be courteous and flexible when you approach them and, above all, be transparent. Even if you have a dislike for the person you are interviewing, they are still doing you a favour and you may need to get back to them at some stage in time. Be an active listener and open to digressions: often useful information is provided in side conversations; open ended questions can take the conversation to unexpected places.
- Libraries; university libraries and national archives are likely to have access to large databases and archives. Librarians may be able to help with the research or, at the very least, point you in the right direction.

- For older students, national agencies are likely to hold data you are looking for. This can be very tricky, as depending on the information requested, the agency may not want or may not be allowed to release the information. There are a few ways to ask for the information, and these may vary from country to country (e.g. the Freedom of Information Act in the UK, <https://www.gov.uk/make-a-freedom-of-information-request/the-freedom-of-information-act>)

SAMPLE FROM NORTHERN IRELAND

Project name: FAKE NEWS - TRUE OR FALSE?

Children in Northern Ireland wanted to find out how do people know if Fake News is true or false. They collected samples of Fake News to design a survey to test out people's responses. They collected responses from 230 people and the results were analysed and displayed on a results poster. They also developed a PowerPoint outlining how they made a movie around Fake News. It was about a boy who set up a fake website and received lots of views. However, he was caught by his father and his fake online world came to an end!

Project link from the WYRED platform:

<https://platform.wyredproject.eu/community/northern-ireland-community/project/fake-news-true-or-false>

SAMPLE FROM ITALY

Project name: WHAT'S THE PERCEPTION OF MIGRANT STUDENTS AND HOW DOES THE VIRTUAL WORLD AFFECT REALITY ON THIS TOPIC?

In this research we try to find the answers to these questions: How is diversity in the classroom and in the non-school environment? How is the theme dealt within the family? What do they learn from the media?

The aim of the research Project is to investigate the perception and opinion of middle school children about the issues of tolerance and discrimination by referring to their personal experience. The research tackles the perception of young Italian and foreign students on the subject of tolerance towards opinions and cultures which are "different from theirs."

Project link from the WYRED platform:

<https://platform.wyredproject.eu/community/tolerance-towards-different-culturesopinions/project/whats-perception-migrant-students-and>

4. Action research

If you want to research a problem to find a solution so you can take action to solve that problem, then you are going to carry out what can be defined as 'action research'. The idea here is that action will follow research, and that researchers will involve others to take part in the action. The goal is to come up with a solution that can be documented and implemented.

SAMPLE FROM TURKEY

Project name: DON'T BE AFRAID KNOW WELL!

In this study, the problems of refugees and defectors who are the most popular today and disturb the community structure in many aspects in terms of political and social were handled. However, preliminary the basis of this problem was examined and the prejudice towards defectors and refugees who live negative tyrannizing over and marginalizing in streets, living areas, schools e.g. basically result from the lack of education and not knowing them well. Besides, this kind of tyrannizing and exclusion, refugees (especially Syrians) in our country live war trauma, the stress of their scattered lives and these stress factors trigger for mental health problems. Apart from these, the possibility of permanent settlement of refugees in cities becomes another anxiety. This also has to become a potential development. The problems that were handled in the study was restricted 'Syrians who live in Zeytinburnu, Istanbul'. The study was conducted with the students at 14-15 age. 14-15 age group are affected mostly from social media, family and environment and have the most potential prejudice. As procedure, we aimed to supply the easiness of living with defectors changing the perception via focus interviews named 'preliminary interview' and 'the last interview'. At the end of preliminary interview, workshops about 'minorities and respect towards differences' e.g. were given to the first focus group by Bilgi University academicians. We proved perception could be changed uniquely by education by giving workshops only to the first focus group aside from the second focus group. It was determined that stereotypes were changed during the last interview at the end of workshops. The students who got education in the first focus group showed off their sensitivity about this subject via posters, banners, leaflets that they prepared at the workshops.

Project link from the WYRED platform:

<https://platform.wyredproject.eu/community/do%C4%9Fa-community/project/doga-school-projects>

SAMPLE FROM ISRAEL

Project name: BRIDGING THE GAPS AND DISAGREEMENTS

The Students of the Tel Aviv Youth University, representing the young generation perspective, pointed out dilemmas and issues that they'll present as a challenge to the decision-makers, locally and globally. The first phase was a journey of learning and researching various problems

related to the current reality and the future of the Israeli society, through tours and lectures in a variety of subjects.

During their "journey of learning" they were inspired by a lecture discussing the idea of "The 4 Israeli tribes" - a phrase that was coined by the President of Israel to modify four groups that Israel is disintegrating into: the ultra-Orthodox, the national religious, the Arab sector and the secular Jewish sector. Using their experience of living and working in the digital world, the students claim that social networks are catalysts for hate speech but can also be a promoter of social change.

In the second phase of the activity, the students received practical tools that enabled them to learn different ways to express their opinions, engage large audiences and reach decision makers like lectures about social activity, lobbying, media workshops and more.

With that knowledge on their mind, the young students wrote down a brief for their campaign: they explained the issue, its relevance to the future society, and the ways that they were willing to act.

The students decided to outline a program for a blog which will describe their experiences in the project where Arabs and Jews, religious and secular, succeeded in bridging the gaps and disagreements - studying and living together

Project link from the WYRED platform: <https://platform.wyredproject.eu/community/tel-aviv-summer-youth-university/project/bridging-gaps-and-disagreements>

5. Solidarity projects

A solidarity project is different from other research types only by its goal: to promote care or understanding for disadvantaged groups, usually by involving the wider community. This also means that in the long run, the target group should become stronger and less dependent on the support of the project. Solidarity can be seen as support given to individuals or groups who cannot address their basic needs without outside help. It is not charity, as it is a constructive and long-term effort, so that the beneficiaries can eventually become independent.

SAMPLE FROM TURKEY

Project name: MOBILE APPLICATION TO DETECT BATTERY POWERED/ELECTRICAL WHEEL CHAIRS CHARGING STATIONS

This developed mobile application programme is prepared for physically handicapped people to reach the closest wheelchair charging station easily and fleetly from the place they are in order to make physically handicapped people's life easier. The mobile programming was prepared in Hybrid language and during the preparation process it was benefited from the html5, JavaScript, .NET and MySQL Server libraries on the application Adobe Phone gap / Cordova. Also, this application has a web-based control panel. The application could be downloaded free from Google Store for Android systems. Today this programme could be reachable for all physically handicapped people for the sake of actively used mobile phones. In the content of the application, it could be possible to find the closest charging station. Besides, it would be possible to inform inactive charging station and remove this inactive station from the system. It can be possible to take the address of the stations from Yandex maps. At the same time, it was designed to be developed by all the users with smart learning. Owing to this feature, new stations could be included in the database easily. This application presents the opportunity to upload the station that the users realize to the system at once if they also detect the inexact station they can inform the system about this station. By means of technology, the application could keep itself up-to-date in the world that the needs could be changeable at any time.

Project link from the WYRED platform:

<https://platform.wyredproject.eu/community/do%C4%9Fa-community/project/mobile-application-detect-battery-poweredelectrical-wheel-chairs>

6. Ethnographic projects

Ethnography is the study of how humans behave with each other and on their own, of how certain groups see the world, what their actions or reactions can be in certain context, etc. In an ethnographic project, the researchers must try to see the world like a member of the group they are researching. This can be done observing people, by talking to them, by doing what they are doing. The goal is not to teach the group something new, but simply to describe and understand them.

SAMPLE FROM NORTHERN IRELAND

Project name: WHY DO PEOPLE HACK?

Children in Northern Ireland were thinking of a number of questions to do with HACKING - Who, what, where, how and why? They decided to research some famous hackers to find out

the answers to some of their questions. Then they composed and performed a RAP to demonstrate their findings.

Project link from the WYRED platform:

<https://platform.wyredproject.eu/community/northern-ireland-community/project/why-do-people-hack>

SAMPLE FROM NORTHERN IRELAND

Project name: WHY DO CHILDREN TELL LIES ON THE INTERNET?

A group of 8 - 10-year-old children in Northern Ireland investigate the research question - Why do children tell lies on the internet? They involved 154 of their peer group in the research. the children were actively engaged in the research cycle which culminated in the production of 2 research posters. The questionnaire was designed and developed by the children to help them collect and collate the opinions of their peer group. 154 questionnaires were completed and returned for analysis.

Project link from the WYRED platform: <https://platform.wyredproject.eu/community/why-do-children-tell-lies-internet/project/why-do-children-tell-lies-internet>

7. Additional project methods, to be added by partner organisations during the 1st Cycle

SAMPLE FROM UNITED KINGDOM

Project name: BRIGHTON HOUSING DIALOGUE EXPANDS STUDENTS' MINDS

He asked if I could come again next week and help him finish off the film. I could see his imagination had been sparked and he was committed to completing his creative project to express what he had found out. I think in this instance it was the opportunity to use his creativity to further explore an issue that allowed him to reflect and empathise with the people behind the statistics.

Watching his film in front of his peers was also an empowering experience. To be witnessed expressing your voice gives it more power. I hope that participating in this WYRED process helped the students to think for themselves, to follow their train of thought through a variety of mediums, to find out facts and to develop their belief in their ability to create, communicate and enjoy the research process.

Project link from the WYRED platform: <https://en.wyredproject.eu/2018/02/19/brighton-housing-dialogue-expands-students-minds/>

3 Step-by-step guide to the research methods: school examples

The following guide shall give you a more detailed and hands-on approach to the research methods.

Table 2: Step-by-step guide

STEPS	EXPLANATIONS
<p>STEP 1 Identify a topic</p>	<p>A quick-fire round of questions to students about their extra-curricular interests.</p> <p>e.g. <i>What's on your mind? What would you change about your school/town/the street you live in</i>, etc. At this stage, let students identify a topic with a brief description. The initial focus is on choosing</p>

	<p>a topic, any topic, that may be of interest to the learners. From there, the moderator will gently direct their attention to find a connection with the focus topics of the 3rd Cycle of the WYRED project: <i>Internet safety, Living on Social Media, Digital Participation and Gender issues</i></p>
<p>STEP 2 Analyse the topic, re-formulate the topic</p>	<p>Once a topic of interest has been identified, the actual area of research can be narrowed down with some guiding questions. e.g. <i>How many stakeholders do you think you will actually be able to interview? What artefacts do you intend to produce? etc.</i> Typically, this will lead to the topic being re-formulated. However, it is important to bear in mind, and to let students know, that the topic can be re-formulated at any future stage, once new knowledge has been brought in.</p>
<p>STEP 3 Choose a research methodology</p>	<p>At this stage it is useful to run through all or at least some of the research methods listed under 'Generative Research Methods' above. Although some of the methods may seem very similar, it is helpful to point out that not all are equally suited, depending on the topic chosen. It is crucial at this stage that students understand the meaning of '<i>generative</i>' in this context, i.e. that the research project will generate a tangible outcome to be shared with others.</p>
<p>STEP 4 Define next steps</p>	<p>Once it has been decided what the students want to do, they are going to draft a proposal of how to do it.</p> <p>Students will need to be aware that the actions they are planning ought to be aligned with the outcomes. As an example, if students suggest to conduct face-to-face interviews, and their intended outcome is to increase awareness, they will need to plan further actions, building on the outcome and interpretation of the interviews.</p> <p>It is useful to introduce the concept of artefacts at this stage: every project should generate one or more tangible results, which can be presented in any format (e.g. written report, images, drawings, prototypes, graphs illustrating survey results, etc.). Artefacts need to be planned ahead, so that their production becomes a natural process inside the project life cycle.</p> <p>Furthermore, students may want to start answering the following question: What will we do with the results of our research? Since one of the main goals of any research is to share the outcome, students should start thinking how and where to publicise their findings. The WYRED platform will be an automatic first choice, but there are many other options available (e.g. school publications, local papers, social media, YouTube, etc.)</p>

<p>STEP 4</p> <p>Carry out the next steps</p>	<p>Students will draft a timetable of the various steps. Often it is useful to start with a deadline, and work backwards to allocate tasks along a timeline. If the timeline is too short, students may seek to extend the deadline, or to drop some steps, or to change their research topic altogether. This is all part of a learning process, so this not result in wasted time.</p>
<p>STEP 4</p> <p>Carry out the next steps</p>	<p>Moderators will follow learners as closely as possible, but only intervening when asked to do so by the students, or when a critical situation arises (e.g. learners are stuck, are abandoning their project, are about to undertake unethical actions, etc.). It is important that students document every single step in great detail, as this will greatly help them in summarising their findings and in creating their artefacts. Part of the documentation, e.g. pictures showing some of the activities undertaken, dummy prototypes created during an ideation workshop, etc. are in fact also artefacts which can be preserved and showcased to illustrate the concept of the project.</p>
<p>STEP 5</p> <p>Summarise</p>	<p>To wrap up the activity, students will draft a simple report structured along the following sections: what was done, how it was done, what the outcome was and, if applicable, what will be or should be done to further research the topic.</p> <p>At this stage, all artefacts collected during the project will be listed.</p>
<p>STEP 6</p> <p>Publicise the outcome</p>	<p>As previously mentioned, the first port of call to publicise any WYRED project should be the WYRED website on https://wyredproject.eu/category/research-projects/. See below for further instructions on how to use the platform.</p> <p>However, further avenues should already have been explored under Step 4, in order to maximise the exposure for the various projects.</p> <p>When publicising the results, bear in mind to not only focus on the outcome of the research project, but take into account the journey covered and the commitment and passion showed by the students.</p>
<p>ADDITIONAL STEPS</p>	<p>The above steps are listed for reference purpose only. Some students may choose to skip a step, or to merge two or more steps in to one, or to further break down some steps or indeed to add a few more.</p>

The following examples are based on translated input provided by students at the Anatolian Religious High School for Girls in Çamlıca, Istanbul. The examples shown are not comprehensive, as the scope of the exercise was limited to verify the students' understanding of the toolkit and to gather useful feedback from a specific target group. Instead, the intention is to illustrate how students interpreted the instructions shown in the introduction of Annex 7, and how moderators provided input to help students on their way.

A. Social responsibility and social media

STEPS	EXPLANATIONS
<p>STEP 1</p> <p>Identify a topic</p> <p>Student's input: <i>Do young people have a sense of social responsibility?</i></p> <p>Topic defined as: <i>Awareness of Social Responsibility among students aged 14-16 at Imam Hatip High School Girls in Çamlıca.</i></p>	<p>A quick-fire round of questions to students about their extra-curricular interests generated an interesting conversation among the students and between the students and the moderator. The role of the moderator was two-fold:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - gently direct the conversation to cover one or more of the four topics identified for the 3rd Cycle of the WYRED project (<i>Internet safety, Living on Social Media, Digital Participation and Gender issues</i>) - help students to frame their research question so that it remains ambitious but also realistic
<p>STEP 2</p> <p>Analyse the topic, re-formulate the topic</p> <p>Student's input: <i>What percentage of young people use social media? And how many are aware of social responsibility projects in social media?</i></p> <p>Topic re-defined as: <i>Social Media usage and Social Responsibility activities among</i></p>	<p>Having chosen a topic, students start thinking about the connotations of the chosen topic, either spontaneously or after being prompted. Often this leads to a newly formulated research topic and goal.</p> <p>In this example, the students suggested to 'calculate and list percentages of social media usage'. The idea behind it was to look for direct connections between usage of social media and activities on social responsibility, based on the assumption that active social users are more likely to be exposed to social responsibility activities and, therefore, to be more likely to take part in them.</p>

<p><i>students aged 14-16 at Imam Hatip High School for Girls in Çamlıca.</i></p>	
<p>STEP 3 Choose a research methodology</p>	<p>This group of students did not choose a specific methodology. They indicated their work may sit well under category 1 (Classic Research Project)</p>
<p>STEP 4 Define next steps</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Prepare a list of social responsibility activities that will attract the attention of young people • Produce and distribute leaflets to raise awareness about social responsibility • Carry out surveys in our school and in schools close to us, to see if the activities were carried out. 	<p>The students came up with an interesting list of activities. Instead of curbing their enthusiasm by forcing them to define exact timelines and scope for each of their activities, they were motivated to write down a long list of potential activities. They were then asked to pick their favourites, those they thought would have the biggest impact. As a next step, they would then have had to describe the time and resources needed to carry out the chosen activities.</p>

B. The impact of social media on young people's communication skills

STEPS	EXPLANATIONS
<p>STEP 1 Identify a topic Student's input: Young people cannot express themselves Topic defined as: Are young people capable of expressing themselves in a way that they are heard and understood by adults?</p>	<p>The topic was turned into a question, in order to avoid bias. When discussing the topic further, it became apparent that students were afraid that social media hampers their communication skills: <i>Because of social media, the language used by young people has changed. They use abbreviations and different ways to spell words.</i></p>

<p>STEP 2</p> <p>Analyse the topic, re-formulate the topic</p> <p>Student's input: <i>What is the impact on social relations resulting from social media's impact on the language used by young people?</i></p> <p>Topic re-defined as: <i>Does the language used in social media have an impact on the quality of human communication?</i></p>	<p>This group of students was particularly interested in how young people interact, and how the way they use social media impacts on the quality of their interactions. They feared an erosion of typically human aspects of communication, such as empathy, respect, feeling enriched, etc.</p>
<p>STEP 3</p> <p>Choose a research methodology</p>	<p>This group of students did not choose a specific methodology. They indicated their work may sit well under category 1 (Classic Research Project)</p>
<p>STEP 4</p> <p>Define next steps</p> <p>We will analyse difficulties of young people while expressing themselves, and measure any potential change in young people's self-confidence. To do this, we will:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Survey students aged 14-19, their teachers as well as their parents • Read, analyse and summarise relevant literature (articles, books, but also documentaries) • Prepare and distribute relevant surveys • • The final result will be a written report summarising the findings, 	<p>At this stage, the students have a fairly good idea of what they want to do, and how they want to do it. They may need to timetable the next steps, and then they are ready to start work.</p>

<p>and formulating recommendations</p>	
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C.

STEPS	EXPLANATIONS
<p>STEP 1</p> <p>Identify a topic</p> <p>Student's input: Determine the positive and negative effects of rote education, by comparing this teaching method with an experience and visualisation-based system. (I will involve two different classes of 8th graders).</p> <p>Topic defined as: Positive and negative impact of rote learning among 8th graders.</p>	<p>At first sight, the topic of interest does not seem aligned with the 3rd Cycle of WYRED. However, the students seemed very passionate about it, so instead of brushing it away, the research question was refined. In particular, it was noted that today's education is inextricably linked to technology and the internet anyway.</p>
<p>STEP 2</p> <p>Analyse the topic, re-formulate the topic</p> <p>Student's input: <i>What can students memorise from lessons? (I will ask students different questions about Turkish language and history, and also make them carry out a chemical experiment).</i></p> <p>Topic re-defined as: <i>Impact of rote learning on information retention of 8th graders.</i></p>	<p>At this stage, the research topic was further refined. Specific attention was paid to various techniques of rote learning, e.g. repetitive reading, reading aloud, singing formulas in songs, copying the text by hand or by typing it, etc. Questions about reading on paper vs reading on screen, writing on paper vs writing on screen were also asked, thereby naturally establishing a link with the 3rd Cycle topics of WYRED.</p>
<p>STEP 3</p> <p>Choose a research methodology</p> <p>Action Research Method</p>	<p>Based on the description of the methods presented, this group opted for the Action Research method. The moderator simply took note of it, as it appeared to be a pertinent choice.</p>

<p>STEP 4</p> <p>Define next steps</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none">• Connect to teachers and school leaders, in order to have access to students to carry out the necessary activities• Identify 6 classes and split them in two groups• Produce three short lesson plans, covering:<ul style="list-style-type: none">- spelling of complex words;- historical background to a famous battle (tbd);- an experiment in Chemistry.• The lesson plans will be structured in two different ways:<ul style="list-style-type: none">- learners will have to memorise data provided by heart (rote learning, focusing on mnemonic skills)- learners will have to visualise the topics, and to describe them in writing.• The learning outcomes will be compared. Retention of knowledge gain will also be tested, after a set period.	<p>Rather typically, the students immersed themselves immediately in the actions they were planning to carry out, without giving much thought to the necessary pre-requisites. In this case, the moderator pointed them to the first step, that is to seek permission and support to carry out their chosen activities in their school.</p>
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4 Step-by-step guide to register a project on the WYRED platform, and to upload relevant artefacts

The WYRED platform allows participants to upload projects and artefacts, and thereby to share outcomes and viewpoints with stakeholders across Europe and beyond. This will automatically increase the exposure of your project; a significant amount of people will see it and mention it in their social media presence. In addition, the WYRED platform allows you to conduct meaningful discussions with peers from different countries on topics of your interest, and to connect with international youth organisations.

4.1 Accessing the platform

The WYRED platform (García-Holgado & García-Peñalvo, 2018; García-Peñalvo, 2016a, 2018; García-Peñalvo & Durán-Escudero, 2017; García-Peñalvo, García-Holgado, Vázquez-Ingelmo, & Seoane-Pardo, 2018) can be accessed from the following link, which you may want to bookmark:

<https://platform.wyredproject.eu/>

This is the landing page, which is available in all languages represented in the WYRED project.

Picture 1: WYRED platform main access page

Should you not remember your password, you can click on the link provided: 'Forgot your password'. If you do this, you will land on the following page:

Picture 2: password request page

Simply by submitting your e-mail address, you will receive a new password. Be sure to use the same e-mail address you used to register on the platform.

4.2 The homepage and its subsections

After login, you will land on the homepage.

Picture 3: WYRED homepage

The main body of the homepage is the **Welcome to WYRED** part, which gives you an instant overview of the latest news and any messages from your communities.

Picture 4: The Welcome to WYRED part

Do not forget to visit the Welcome Community, which includes all users registered on the WYRED platform. This is the place you can use to chat to anyone on the platform about your favourite WYRED subject; simply select a user by clicking on their name, and away you chat.

Picture 5: Welcome community

Going back to the homepage, you will notice that at the top, in the black horizontal bar (also known as 'horizontal navigation bar'), there is a menu with 5 main links:

- Home
- Communities
- Projects
- Events
- Help

The **Communities** link allows you to see the public WYRED communities:

Picture 6: Communities

At time of writing, there were 31 accessible communities on the platform. To join a community, select the title of a community and click on “Subscribe to Group” on the right-hand side of the resulting landing page. This will trigger a request sent to the facilitator of the community, and once they have accepted your request, you will automatically have joined that community.

Subscribe to
group

Picture 7: Community access

Under **Projects** you will be able to see all the projects uploaded on the platform. At the time of writing, there were 115 publicly accessible projects on platform. There were also some private projects on platform, which are accessible only for the private communities in which they have been developed.

Public projects

Please fill in the **Inclusion Questionnaire** before you go on.

Public projects: 115
Private projects are only available inside the private communities in which they are developed.

Etiketler

Dil: - Herhangi -
Sıralama anahtarı: Gönderi tarihi
Sıralama: Azalan
Uygula Sifirle

Democracy in schools

The project aims to find out if these democratic structures in schools are present, are they working actively and question students whether these structures improve their overall efficiency.
[\(Read more\)](#)

Why do people hack?

Children in Northern Ireland were thinking of a number of questions to do with HACKING - Who, what, where, how and why?
[\(Read more\)](#)

Fake News - true or false?

Children in Northern Ireland wanted to find out how do people know if Fake News is true or false. They collected samples of Fake News to design a survey to test out people's responses.
[\(Read more\)](#)

Accessibility of higher education

The Students of the Tel Aviv Youth University - a project which enables periphery high-school students to take academic courses on the university - have explored the future society.
[\(Read more\)](#)

Bridging the gaps and disagreements

The Students of the Tel Aviv Youth University, representing the young generation perspective, pointed out dilemmas and issues that they'll present as a challenge to the decision-makers, locally and
[\(Read more\)](#)

Cyberbullying - NI Perspective

Children in Northern Ireland wanted to find out why people Cyberbully. If Cyberbullying makes the bully feel good and why they think it is okay to do this.
[\(Read more\)](#)

THE GREEN CAMPUS

[\(Read more\)](#)

#Equals

The Students of the Tel Aviv Youth University - a project which enables periphery high-school students to take academic courses on the university - have explored the future society.
[\(Read more\)](#)

Picture 8: Public projects

Going back to the homepage, you will find two sections on the right side:

- Your Communities
- Last projects

Picture 9: Right hand side of the homepage, Your Communities and Last projects

You may also see the section called “Facilitator tools”, which can only be accessed by facilitators.

Under “Your communities”, you will see all the communities you have joined.

The section called “Last projects” will take you to the latest projects uploaded on the platform.

4.3 Uploading your research projects

In order to upload a research project, you will need to access the relevant community, on the right side there are public content.

Picture 10: Homepage of your community

By selecting 'Publish content', you will be shown a screen where you can enter all the relevant information and content.

Picture 11: Screenshots of the project submission section

Please remember that all fields with an asterisk (*) are compulsory and must be completed. Ideally, for every project there will be a series of artefacts to showcase your work (e.g. a report, video, presentation, etc.). To add them with your submission, select “Add another item” and upload the file in question. Once you have completed all the fields, please remember to click on “Save”.

The screenshot shows the 'Results' form in the WYRED platform. It includes a 'Result title' field, a 'File *' section with a 'Dosya Seç' button and a 'Yükle' button, and a 'Result description' section with a rich text editor. The 'Result visibility *' dropdown is set to 'All WYRED platform users'. A 'Kaldır' button is visible at the bottom of the form. Below the form, there is a 'Publish the results related to this project.' section with a '+ Başka bir öğe ekle' button.

Picture 12: Adding an artefact when uploading a project

As shown on Picture 12, once you have completed the upload and submission of content, you will be asked to choose the visibility level for your project. There are 3 options to choose from: visible to community members only, to all WYRED platform users and to everyone internal and external to the WYRED platform.

4.4 Accessing a research project

All public projects are accessible from the **Projects** link found on the top of the homepage. The project page contains information about the total number of projects available, as well as a set of filters to allow you to refine your search. The projects are listed as set of thumbnails. By clicking on the title of your chosen project, you will be able to access it and review some detailed information. You will also be able to see the project report, any pictures and videos, as well as presentations about the project. In addition, you can cast your vote to express how much you like the project, and award from 1 to 5 stars accordingly, together with your comments.

Democracy in schools

The project aims to find out if these democratic structures in schools are present, are they working actively and question students whether these structures improve their overall efficiency. It also aims to understand what students think about these types of structures, collect their suggestions and their complaints.

Tags: education |

Language: English

Vote: Henüz oy kullanılmadı

Sonuçlar

Democracy in schools
[Democracy in schools.pdf](#)
Democracy in schools
[MVI_8888.mp4](#)

Community

This project has been developed in the community **Doğa Community**.

Yeni yorum ekle

Adınız gizemogyuz

Konu

Re: Democracy in schools

Comment *

Full HTML

Kaydet

[Metin biçimleri hakkında daha fazla bilgi](#)

Picture 13: Vote and comment

Annex 1: Support template for the research activity

Refine a Research Question	<i>e.g. Does the echo chamber effect distort our perception of current affairs?</i>
Research Method	<i>e.g. Action Research</i>
Data collection tools	<i>e.g. check lists (quantitative); observations/interviews (qualitative)</i>
Step 1 Setting the context	<i>e.g. The internet provides access to a vast amount of all sorts of news; algorithms and news aggregators seem to expose users to selected news stories only, with the risk of providing a distorted picture of current affairs</i>
Step 2 Mapping	<i>e.g.</i> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - <i>What sites do young people visit, and why?</i> - <i>Which sites do they visit most often?</i> - <i>Which alternative sites can be suggested, to achieve a more balanced exposure to news?</i>
Steps 3 Create & Share	<i>e.g. produce an infographic, summarising the above</i>
Steps 4 Reflection & discussion	<i>(review data with target group, discuss background information, motivation, etc.; analyse potential action; summarise)</i>
	 Activity Toolkit - Handout example 01.pdf
	 Activity Toolkit - Handout example 02.pdf

(Adapted from the Points of Light Foundation "Mapping Youth Programs for Youth Involvement" handout)

Annex 2: Infographics for young participants

How to get Started

BEGIN

YOUR MOTIVATION

Think about 2-3 things you would like to change, and of people you may want to involve.

REVIEW

Scan through the list of Research Methods, and match them with your motivation to change things..

THE TOOLS

CHOOSE

DISCUSS YOUR CHOICE

Identify 1-2 methods you find most appealing. Discuss them with your Coordinator, to fully appreciate what they entail

GO!

TAKE THE FIRST STEP

Use the step-by-step guide to get started. Give yourself a timeline, and periodically review progress with your Coordinator.

RECORD

Remember to record every step you take, and to write down lots of information. This will make it easier to create the final report, in whichever format you have chosen, and to track back your work, if needed.

RECORD AND REPORT

PUBLISH

PUBLISH YOUR WORK - CONGRATULATIONS: YOU ARE NOW A PUBLISHED AUTHOR!

RESEARCH METHODS

THE TRADITIONAL RESEARCH

Research projects typically explore under-researched areas; they can also replicate an existing study in a different setting. They apply and test ideas in the real world. To be successful, you will need to be systematic, and apply the newly acquired knowledge in the real world.

CREATIVE PROJECTS

Similarly to the traditional research projects, but with particular attention on the collaboration between researchers, and on the creation of original design and artwork.

JOURNALISTIC APPROACH

A journalistic research is undertaken alone or in a team; key to its success are accuracy (get the facts right), impartiality (serve no interest but the truth) and accountability (if necessary, admit to errors and correct them). Take on the role of a reporter and conduct primary and secondary research, incl. photographic evidence. Tell the story so the majority of citizens can read it - your narrative skills will be tested.

ACTION RESEARCH

A process of inquiring about problems and taking actions to solve them. It makes use of several methods and requires participation of many stakeholders. It is based on the assumption that knowledge is always gained through action and for action. The goal is to come up with step by step solutions to existing problems.

SOLIDARITY PROJECTS

Solidarity projects promote mutual care and understanding. They target underserved groups and work with the support of the whole community. The idea is to empower target groups. Solidarity is support given to individuals or groups, who are reliant on outside help. It is different from charity since solidarity means mutual support, not just financial aid, so that the receivers can become self-reliant over time.

ETHNOGRAPHIC PROJECTS

Ethnography is the study of social interactions, behaviours, and perceptions that occur within groups and communities. The aim is to see the surrounding world from eyes of the target group. This is done through observations and conversations while immersed in the field. Ethnographic projects require a great deal of personal involvement, are very time consuming but can also be great fun.

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Annex 3: Decision-making template for the research activity

Main objective: I want to...	Fitting approaches
... increase knowledge on a topic	1, 2, 3, 6
... define or create new solutions, applications, tools, services, etc.	2, 4, 5
... summarise and publicise findings to a wider audience	1, 3, 6
... promote specific actions	3, 4, 5
... to help empower specific target groups	4, 5, 6
... build bridges with specific target groups	4, 5, 6
Main outcome: My work will result in a ...	
... written report, case study, white paper, blog, article, etc.	1, 3
... video, posters, comics, musical, play, etc.	2, 4, 6
... formal or informal organisation delivering specific services, producing work, etc.	4, 5
... official or unofficial action to address a specific situation	4, 5, 6
Collaboration: I will work mainly with ...	
... young people	2, 3, 4, 5
... my fellow researchers	1, 3, 6
... third party institutions	1, 2, 4, 5, 6
Timelines: I need my work to be completed within ...	
... a week	2, 3
... a month	2, 3
... a quarter	1, 3, 4
... a year or longer	1, 4, 5, 6
Impact: I want to impact mainly	
... public opinion	3, 5
... young people's attitudes and behaviours	2, 4

... adults' attitudes and pre-conceptions	1, 2, 3
... policy makers	1, 3, 5, 6

Annex 4: Support template for the research activity (Adapted from the Points of Light Foundation “Mapping Youth Programs for Youth Involvement” handout)

Refine a Research Question	<i>e.g. Does the echo chamber effect distort our perception of current affairs?</i>
Research Method	<i>e.g. Action Research</i>
Data collection tools	<i>e.g. check lists (quantitative); observations/interviews (qualitative)</i>
Step 1 Setting the context	<i>e.g. The internet provides access to a vast amount of all sorts of news; algorithms and news aggregators seem to expose users to selected news stories only, with the risk of providing a distorted picture of current affairs</i>
Step 2 Mapping	<p><i>e.g.</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - <i>What sites do young people visit, and why?</i> - <i>Which sites do they visit most often?</i> - <i>Which alternative sites can be suggested, to achieve a more balanced exposure to news?</i>
Step 3 Create & Share	<i>e.g. produce an infographic summarising the above</i>
Steps 4 Reflection & discussion	<i>e.g. review data with target group, discuss background information, motivation, etc.; analyse potential action; summarise;</i>
	 Activity Toolkit - Handout example 01.pdf http://www.theinnovationcenter.org/files/Reflect-and-Improve_Toolkit.pdf
	 Activity Toolkit - Handout example 02.pdf https://www.salto-youth.net/downloads/toolbox_tool_download-file-193/CD%20telling%20it%20like%20it%20is%20peer%20education%20and%20training%20manual.pdf

Annex 5: Data collection template framework

<i>EXPERIENCING</i>		<i>ENQUIRING</i>		<i>EXAMINING</i>	
Participation	<i>It helps researchers learn the perspectives held by study populations. It always takes place in community settings, in locations believed to have some relevance to the research questions. The researcher engaged in participant observation tries to learn what life is like for an “insider” while remaining inevitably, an “outsider.”¹</i>	Informal Interview	<i>The wording of the questions and topics to be discussed are not predetermined. These types of interviews often occur spontaneously. It can be conducted face-to-face or by telephone.</i>	Archival documents	<i>It is information specifically collected for bureaucratic procedures and the like – applications, reports, etc. Archives are often stored as paper files or on electronic storage – computer disks, CDs, DVDs, etc. If a researcher collects original data, he or she has more control what data are collected².</i>
Performance & other creative	<i>Drama, exhibition, and video are imaginative and attractive alternatives to the written word.³ These imaginative new approaches can be used to demystify the evaluation process. Using creative arts in evaluation offers opportunities for imaginative ways of understanding programs and creating evaluation knowledge. The creative arts may be used in designing, interpreting, and communicating evaluations.</i>	Structured Formal Interview	<i>Verbally administered questionnaires, in which a list of predetermined questions are asked, with little or no variation and with no scope for follow-up questions to responses that warrant further elaboration. They are relatively quick and easy to administer.</i>	Journals	<i>A journal is a scholarly publication containing articles written by researchers, professors and other experts. Journals focus on a specific discipline or field of study. Unlike newspapers and magazines, journals are intended for an academic or technical audience, not general readers.⁴ The journal writing is the effective tool to make connections with your knowledge and others.</i>
Story Telling	<i>STORYTELLING is the art in which a teller conveys a message, truths, information, knowledge, or wisdom to an audience – often subliminally – in an entertaining way, using whatever skills, (musical, artistic, creative) or props he chooses, to enhance the audience’s enjoyment, retention and understanding of the message conveyed. Stories are sometimes told purely for joy and delight.⁵ Storytelling can help researcher to experience their research process with enjoy.</i>	Questionnaires	<i>They usually include a set of standardized questions that explore a specific topic and collect information about demographics, opinions, attitudes, or behaviours. They can contain short closed-ended questions (multiple choice) or broad open-ended questions. Questionnaires are used to collect data from a large group of subjects on a specific topic. Currently, many questionnaires are developed and administered online. Three popular programs that allow you to create online surveys are Google Forms, Survey Monkey, and Poll Everywhere.</i>	Maps	<i>A map is a symbolic depiction emphasizing relationships between elements of some space, such as objects, regions, or themes. (Wikipedia) Researchers can use maps to collect and present their data more regular.</i>

Self Reflection	<i>Self-reflection is like looking into a mirror and describing what you see. It is a way of assessing yourself, your ways of working and how you study. To put it simply 'reflection' means to think about something. Reflecting and composing a piece of self-reflective writing is becoming an increasingly important element to any form of study or learning.⁶</i>	Attitude Scales	<i>Attitude scale is a measure or assessment used to assess an attitude - usually for the purpose of comparison.⁷</i>	Audio & Video Tapes	<i>In research process videos can be used in a number of ways such as participatory video, videography, video interviews and elicitation and video-based fieldwork. The ability of a video to fix something in its time and its place have an interesting effect in that it can re-awaken the memories and experiences of a researcher or participant. Also, video can support an exploratory research design and extended data discovery. It can be 're-opened' for later analysis and capture things not noticed at the time of being present.⁸</i>
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¹ *Qualitative Research Methods: A Data Collector's Field Guide*

² <http://ctb.ku.edu/en/table-of-contents/evaluate/evaluate-community-interventions/archival-data/main>

³ Curtis, L., J. Springett, and A. Kennedy. 2001. *Evaluation in Urban Settings: the challenge of healthy cities. In Evaluation in Health Promotion: principle and perspectives, edited by I. Rootman and M. Goodstadt: World Health Organization Regional Office for Europe.*

⁴ University of Victoria, <http://www.uvic.ca/library/research/tips/journal/index.php>

⁵ Berice Dudley, 'What is Storytelling', <https://www.australianstorytelling.org.au/storytelling-articles/t-z/what-is-storytelling-berice-dudley>

⁶ Open University, <http://www.open.ac.uk/choose/unison/develop/my-skills/self-reflection>

⁷ What is attitude scale? definition of attitude scale (psychology dictionary) <http://psychologydictionary.org/attitude-scale/>

⁸ Carey Jewitt, 'An introduction to using video for research' National Centre for Research Methods Working Paper 03/12, Institute of Education, London, March 2012. http://eprints.ncrm.ac.uk/2259/4/NCRM_workingpaper_0312.pdf

<p>Intentional Conversation</p>	<p><i>Conversation has been seen as a method of research. It can be a research methodology in collaborative action research with sharing of knowledge and the growth of understanding occurs through meaning making process. Conversation occurs between and among people and it is a cooperative venture. New understanding arises through conversation.</i></p> <p><i>Conversation help to bring the light thoughts and ideas, facilitate communication with each others, exchange of knowledge and generation of understanding. Also, it helps to make decisions.⁹</i></p>	<p>Standardized Tests</p>	<p><i>A Standardized test is a test that is given in a consistent or “standard” manner. Standardized tests are designed to have consistent questions, administration procedures, and scoring procedures. Standardized tests come in many forms, such as standardized interviews, questionnaires, or directly administered intelligence tests. The main benefit of standardized tests is they are typically more reliable and valid than non-standardized measures. They often provide some type of “standard score” which can help interpret how far a child’s score ranges from the average.¹⁰</i></p>	<p>Field note observations & Reflections</p>	<p><i>Field notes refer to transcribed notes or the written account derived from data collected during observations and interviews. There are many styles of field notes, but all field notes generally consist of two parts: descriptive in which the observer attempts to capture a word-picture of the setting, actions and conversations; and reflective in which the observer records thoughts, ideas, questions and concerns based on the observations and interviews.</i></p> <p><i>Field notes should be written as soon as possible after the observation and/or interviews.¹¹</i></p>
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⁹ Allan Fedman, ‘Conversation As Methodology in Collaborative Action Research’, School of Education University of Massachusetts, <http://people.umass.edu/~afeldman/ActionResearchPapers/Feldman1999.PDF>
¹⁰ Johnson Center, http://www.johnson-center.org/downloads/pdfs/What_is_a_Standardized_Test.pdf
¹¹ Observation and Field Notes, https://hci.cs.siu.edu/NSF/Files/TeachingPD/How_CI_Observation%20and%20Field%20Notes.pdf

Referencias

- García-Holgado, A., & García-Peñalvo, F. J. (2018). *WYRED Platform, the ecosystem for the young people*. Paper presented at the HCI International 2018, Las Vegas, NV, USA. <https://youtu.be/TRDjN5boky8>
- García-Peñalvo, F. J. (2016a). *WP3 WYRED Platform Development*. Salamanca, Spain: GRIAL Research group. Retrieved from <https://goo.gl/A98Q8v>
- García-Peñalvo, F. J. (2016b). The WYRED project: A technological platform for a generative research and dialogue about youth perspectives and interests in digital society. *Journal of Information Technology Research*, 9(4), vi-x.
- García-Peñalvo, F. J. (2017). WYRED Project. *Education in the Knowledge Society*, 18(3), 7-14. doi:10.14201/eks2017183714
- García-Peñalvo, F. J. (2018). *WYRED una plataforma para dar la voz a los jóvenes sobre la influencia de la tecnología en la sociedad actual. Un enfoque de ciencia ciudadana*. Paper presented at the II Congreso Internacional de Tendencias en Innovación Educativa (CITIE 2018), Arequipa (Perú).
- García-Peñalvo, F. J., & Durán-Escudero, J. (2017). Interaction design principles in WYRED platform. In P. Zaphiris & A. Ioannou (Eds.), *Learning and Collaboration Technologies. Technology in Education. 4th International Conference, LCT 2017. Held as Part of HCI International 2017, Vancouver, BC, Canada, July 9-14, 2017. Proceedings, Part II* (pp. 371-381). Switzerland: Springer International Publishing.
- García-Peñalvo, F. J., García-Holgado, A., Vázquez-Ingelmo, A., & Seoane-Pardo, A. M. (2018). Usability test of WYRED Platform. In P. Zaphiris & A. Ioannou (Eds.), *Learning and Collaboration Technologies. Design, Development and Technological Innovation. 5th International Conference, LCT 2018, Held as Part of HCI International 2018, Las Vegas, NV, USA, July 15-20, 2018, Proceedings, Part I* (pp. 73-84). Cham, Switzerland: Springer.
- García-Peñalvo, F. J., & Kearney, N. A. (2016). Networked youth research for empowerment in digital society. The WYRED project. In F. J. García-Peñalvo (Ed.), *Proceedings of the Fourth International Conference on Technological Ecosystems for Enhancing Multiculturality (TEEM'16) (Salamanca, Spain, November 2-4, 2016)* (pp. 3-9). New York, NY, USA: ACM.
- Griffiths, D., Kearney, N. A., García-Peñalvo, F. J., Seoane-Pardo, A. M., Cicala, F., Gojkovic, T., . . . Zauchner-Studnicka, S. (2017). *Children and Young People Today: Initial Insights from the WYRED Project*. European Union: WYRED Consortium. Retrieved from <https://goo.gl/6unxmD>